

INVESTIGATION OF THE DEFORMATION OF CARBON FIBRE ROVINGS IN CURVED PATHS

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SUMMARY

Stitching carbon multifilament allows reinforcement of composite parts along complex paths. In this work, the deformation of rovings on curved paths, as well as the influence of the seam properties on the distribution of the carbon monofilaments, is investigated. Analytical model and FEA simulation are used and verified with polished cut images.

Keywords: tailored fibre placement, seams, stitching process, carbon roving, distribution, FEA

BACKGROUND

By placing carbon rovings on tailored paths in a dry preform and appending the matrix, a high performing composite material can be created [1, 2]. Using computer controlled machine like in the tailored fibre placement (TFP-) technology, the rovings are placed in position and fixed on the background by stitching. During the stitching process, the cross section geometry of the carbon roving changes under the influence of the forces between the filaments. Especially in curved paths, the deformation of the rovings causes gaps in the later composite parts (see figure 1).

Figure 1: Roving deformations in small radii and provoke inhomogeneities in laminates

The sewing thread applies pressure on the multifilament and influences the geometry, too. In this work, a systematic analyse of the factors, which have influence on the changes in the multifilament geometry, is done to allow in one next step the quantitative analyse of these factors for the composite part. The exact geometry of the monofilaments is important for the prediction of the mechanical properties of the

structure and for better analyse of the delamination and possible defects in the composite material.

For standard textiles with smaller roving deformations and less variation in the roving cross-section a lot of researches have been done [3-6]. The results are useful for designing 2D and 3D fabrics, 3D braided Preforms and non crimp fabrics. Solutions for the TFP-process are still missing.

OPTIMIZATION OF FIBRE ORIENTATION

In order to fully exploit the anisotropic properties of fibre reinforced composites, an optimisation of fibre orientations in textile preforms is necessary. By doing so, an increase of the strength to weight properties of the composites can be achieved. Different methods exist for optimisation of fibre paths in the preforms [7]. The most common ones are genetic algorithms, load path methods and principal stress methods [8].

The material optimization method Computer Aided Internal Optimization (CAIO), developed by Professor Mattheck, orients the fibres locally toward the main stresses [9]. Through line integration of the individual main stress directions continuous fibre directions are generated. Within a few iterations a minimization of the shearing force is reached. At the same time the failure mode changes from matrix cracking to fibre breakage and thus leads to a higher material utilization.

Research at the FIBRE on fibre direction determination is based likewise upon the CAIO method. In order to reach optimal results, the integration of manufacturing restrictions into the optimisation process is required (see figure 2).

Figure 2: FE-Analysis of optimisation fibre direction for TFP-preforms

The external geometry comes from a normal CAD program and is transferred into a FEM model (MSC-NASTRAN). Loads and starting material properties have to be

defined. From the result of local stresses a first tailored roving path is specified in the fibre-program taking the force flow into account. The modified material properties have to be transferred back into the FE-simulation. Now the first loop is closed and the second begins with new stresses inside the material, due to new fibre directions.

The strength and stiffness of the material is locally adapted and again one determines the local tensions and deformations. This cycle repeats itself, until an optimum is reached. If these trajectories are converted directly into fibre paths, a high maximum stress of the composite construction part is expected. This however is not reached as many influences of the production process as well as the material behavior are not considered in the optimization process. This can lead to a strong variation in the fibre volume content in the part.

Different programs exist that help the design engineer to draw roving paths next to the main stress directions. The requirements for a TFP path however are so complex that the actual programs practically ignore the manufacturing requirements of TFP such as:

- the number of starting and end points of roving paths in a preform shall be as small as possible
- rovings shall be placed parallel
- no gaps between rovings
- the weight of the preform shall be homogeneously distributed

Only an integration of the manufacturing and material constraints into the optimization process allows to fully exploiting the material potential. An integration of all boundary conditions could be realized, but due to their complexity only at large research expenditures. This would lead to a large reduction of the manual work, which is required to generate fibre paths and thus to significant reduction of unit construction and development time.

To describe mechanical properties of tailored structures, knowledge about the local properties is of great importance. Different kinds of roving deformations in fibre paths like small curves, sharp turning points, start and end points are depicted geometrically. Important influences of these inhomogeneities to the mechanical properties of structural parts are characterized by examples.

PROPERTIES OF CARBON FIBRE ROVINGS AND CARBON FILAMENTS

Properties of multifilaments can be studied by testing a whole cluster of filaments or selecting single filaments and extrapolating their results on the multifilament. In the following descriptions, both ways were chosen to get a broad overview on carbon roving properties. Tenax HT rovings and Toray T700 rovings have been analysed.

Single fibre tensile test

The tensile test is one of the most common destructive tests for composites. To use this test on single carbon fibres, a test machine is needed that can provide a very firm hold on the ends of the fibre without crushing the brittle material. Using a Dia-Stron tensile tester, the sample is glued to the holding device. There is dependence between the gauge length and the strength of the tested filament [10], the so called size effect. To keep that

effect as little as possible, small sample lengths are beneficial. The size effect makes it difficult to calculate the tensile strength of a roving based on the values of single filaments. Since carbon filaments fail at an elongation around 2% and breaking forces around 0.25 N [11, 12], good adhesion of the glue to both the plastic and the carbon fibre is necessary. If that connection gives in, the error would be relatively big.

The test results roughly confirmed the values given on the data sheets of the roving producers (Table 1).

Table 1: Single fibre tensile test results compared to data sheet values from the producer

	tensile strength in GPa			E modulus in GPa			breaking elongation in %		
	data sheet	test results		data sheet	test results		data sheet	test results	
		average	standard deviation		average	standard deviation		average	standard deviation
Tenax HTS	4.30	4.90	0.90	238	236	19	1.8	2.2	0.5
Tenax HTA	3.95	4.22	0.82	238	236	13	1.7	1.8	0.4
Toray T 700	4.90	4.63	1.69	230	207	30	2.1	2.3	0.8

Compression and loop test

Compression tests on single carbon fibres are possible these days [13], but still have a high failure rate and are difficult in preparation and execution. It is very probable that the filament does not stay in line but buckles to the side during compression. In this case, there is a change in the stress direction and not compression only anymore. In practical use, there will also hardly ever be an only compression on a roving. Mostly a combined load is found.

For this work, the question of interest was whether a carbon roving takes damage from bending into smaller radiuses. This includes bending and compression stress. To answer that question, a loop test has been done with single carbon filaments. A knot was made into each filament and then the ends were pulled like for a tensile test. The knot got tighter and at some point, the material failed. At the breaking point, the knot was barely visible anymore, showing that a very small radius is needed to break carbon fibres. In most processes with carbon rovings, such stresses are unusual and therefore a material damage because of too tight bending radiuses can be excluded. Nevertheless, often single broken filaments can be found on the surface of a multifilament because of superficial friction and tensile stresses.

Roving tests: Shear test and tensile test across the fibre

While tensile strength tests on single filaments are standardized, tests on properties of multifilaments are rare and often difficult to compare. To find out more about internal

connections between the filaments in a roving, mechanical testing has been done on carefully detached parts of rovings. These tests were shear tests and tensile strength tests across the fibre as well as three point bending tests on rovings.

For shear tests and tensile tests across the fibre, a new test method had to be developed because the fragile rovings cannot simply be fixed in a usual device. The forces to be measured are extremely small in shorter pieces of rovings.

To perform these two tests, a Dia-Stron tensile tester has been used. Into the grip of the machine, a sample holder was inserted, which holds a piece of roving parallel or across to the tensile direction. The roving was fixed onto the plastic sample holder with glue, so that only the edges of the roving were covered. The samples for shear testing were 20 mm, for tensile testing across the fibre 15 mm long due to instrumental limitations.

Figure 3: shear test on roving

Then, the grips moved apart and the roving had to split up along the filaments. Distance and force were measured during the process. With the dimension of the split section, shear strengths and tensile strengths across the fibre could be calculated. The results are that shear strength in rovings is about 20 times higher than tensile strength across the fibre. That effect is comparable to material behaviour of fibre-reinforced composites. If the sizing agent acts as matrix, the roving can be regarded as a breakable one-directional composite.

Roving test: 3-point-bending test

The 3-point-bending-test was done using a testing machine for dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA) from TA Instruments. Rovings were cut to a sample length of 35 mm while the testing distance was 20 mm. In the centre of the sample, the roving was bended down 5 mm. The maximal forces were measured around 0,025 N.

Internal structure of carbon rovings

For validation with the FEA of a dry roving, the preparation affects of the specimen have to be taken into account. The figure below is showing two SEM images of the filament arrangement on the top of a Toho Tenax HTS roving. The imperfection of the parallelism of the filaments in carbon roving had not been quantified with these pictures. Information about the internal filament arrangement are missing.

Figure 4: SEM images of the filament arrangement on the top of a Toho Tenax HTS roving

To get polished micrograph cut images from roving sections, the filaments have to be fixed. This has been done with a low viscosity resin. During the infusion process, the shape of the roving changed. The flat sections were getting smaller and higher; closer to a circle, so the results have to be corrected before comparison with FE results.

Information about the 3D filament arrangement came from computer tomography. At this technology the minimal volumetric pixel (voxel) size depends on the distance of the specimen to the radiator. Because of the width of a complete rovings the minimal voxel size is not small enough to show the filament-filament bonding in detail, but the local filament content could be seen. In figure 5 a cut of the 3D results of the roving is given.

Figure 5: Computer tomography image of a dry carbon rovings

Sizing

The sizing agent on the carbon fibres does not only protect the filaments from mechanical damage and the fibre matrix adhesion, it also plays a very important role in respect to properties like shear strength and bending strength. By fixing monofilaments to each other, the sizing agent acts as a matrix in a composite material. When the roving

is bended, this connection loosens up. Bending strengths of carbon rovings decrease when the bending test is repeated. Once the connection between the monofilaments is broken, it cannot be easily reversed.

Figure 6: Pictures of HTS carbon filaments taken with SEM. The sizing behaviour differs depending on the area.

The age and the composition of the sizing agent are important for its flexibility. On pictures made with SEM, there is a variation in the material behaviour even in one roving. It can be more liquid or almost solid, depending on where the picture is taken. One reason for that would be the fact that the sizing hardens under light irradiation. While the sizing on the surface is already harder, it can still be liquid on lower layers.

Friction

A lot of damage comes to the surface of rovings due to friction. The sizing is supposed to protect the filaments, but the stresses during the machining process are often too great and some of the filaments on the roving surface break. This leads to difficulties with regard to handling the carbon rovings as well as to scattered filaments in later composites. To optimise the roving treatment, studies on the frictional behaviour of rovings need to be done.

NUMERICAL MODELL OF CARBON FIBRE ROVING

A micro mechanical based approach was selected, which describes roving behaviour on basis of material properties of single filaments and physical interactions such as fibre-fibre adhesion, friction between the filaments, etc. To compute the deformation of rovings, the explicit finite element code LS-DYNA was used. A finite element model with a high number of beam elements was created to simulate the connection between the filaments. Input data like tensile, bending and shear strengths are gained by mechanical tests of single carbon fibres and rovings. The results of the deformation analysis have been compared to the forces of mechanical roving tests, the outer geometry and the local fibre volume content in the real deformed roving stitched on TFP-paths.

Because of the high number of elements which are needed to simulate a roving with internal forces, the local filament arrangement and its disposition, a program to create un-deformed rovings was developed. This program was realized in MATLAB and the results were written into an LS-DYNA keyword file. Different filament counts, filament arrangements and cross-sections were regarded.

The first model has ideal parallel filaments and quadratic arrangement of these filaments. The second model is representing a yarn with still parallel filaments but a hexagonal arrangement. For these two models a unit cell was created. The last model has a stochastic filament arrangement regarding the imperfection of the filament orientation based on tomography image analysis. Partly cross sections of these three models are given in the figure below.

Figure 7: Filament arrangement a) rectangular, b) hexagonal and c) stochastic

For the filaments a linear elastic behaviour was defined as it was confirmed by the fibre tensile tests. The carbon filaments of the rovings were represented as Belytschko-Schwer resultant beams. The sewing thread was idealized by a single monofilament and was represented by Belytschko-Schwer beams, too. The displacements of the filaments ends were fixed in main roving direction and without constriction in the roving thickness. Contacts between the filaments were controlled by the LS-Dyna contact option “Automatic General”. It just needed to define only one time for the complete roving as a so called part set.

ROVING CROSS-SECTIONS IN TFP-PATHS

FEA results are compared to data achieved by using computer – tomographic analysis and polished cut images.

An investigation of the distribution of carbon filaments in a roving fixed by using a tailored fibre placement method is done by preparing cross sections of the placed rovings in different radiuses and angles. These are analysed by image analysis and the outer deformation of the roving as well as the positions of the single filaments in the section are detected.

To study polished images, Toray T700 rovings were stitched in half circles to a polyamide background in 10 radiuses from 5 to 55 mm. Two tensions for the sewing yarn were used. Implementing vacuum of 300 mbar, the samples were embedded in Biresin CR81 with hardener CH80-10. When the resin was hard, the samples were cut at 7 angles (see figure 8) and the sections were polished. Pictures of the sections were taken with a light microscope at 100x magnification. Then, an image analysis was done to detect all the carbon filaments in the cross section.

Figure 8: Embedded rovings (left) with cutting angles (middle) and part of a cross section with carbon filaments (right)

The generated databases can be visualised with software to analyse the distribution of the filaments as well as the outer form and cavities. On figure 9, a roving cross section and its visualised data can be seen. The outer form has been sketched as well as a surrounding ellipse. Aligning images of the one roving in all angles, the following observations could be made: The roving becomes narrower the nearer the bending angle is to 90°. Using high tension for the sewing yarn, the roving height does not increase much; therefore a compression of the filaments towards 90° can be seen. As it is deformed, the roving splits up into several bundles of filaments. This behaviour occurs due to the sizing agent which keeps filaments together, but needs to allow them to move during the deformation. In the weak spots, there are cracks and the sizing gives in.

Figure 9: Cross-section of a carbon fibre roving (left) and visualisation of the detected filaments (right)

The drawback of polished images is that the deformation can be analysed only locally. To follow the process along the filaments, 3d pictures of carbon rovings were produced with computed tomography. The samples were stabilized in Biresin CR81 with hardener CH80-10 (low viscosity), like for the polished cutting images. Turning the sample slowly 360°, the detected radiation is evaluated and a 3d image can be created as in figure 10. This method is much faster than analysing cross sections and roving data can be evaluated at any spot in the sample. Still, that method has limits in resolution, especially if the densities of the filaments and the resin are similar.

Figure 10: Computed tomography image of curved carbon rovings

CONCLUSION

The description of the material behaviour is a basic module of each stress analysis and thus an important precondition for the generation of fibre paths for load adapted construction of parts. Basic mechanical and geometrical analyses of roving deformation behaviour have been done. A mechanical model, based on the mesomechanical properties of carbon rovings, has been developed. The discussion of the comparison between the FEA and the image analyses will be published in the presentation form at the ICCM17 conference.

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